

Article 300 and the extent of the immunity and liability of the state in the light of judicial decisions

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Abstract:

This paper explores Article 300 of the Indian Constitution, which governs the legal liability of the Union and State governments in suits and proceedings. The paper traces back to its origins to Clause 214 of the Draft Constitution, rooted in Section 176 of the Government of India Act, 1935, the paper highlights how the Constituent Assembly shaped the legal identity of the State. It examines key judicial pronouncements and the judiciary's interpretations that have clarified the juristic personality of the State and its limited immunity, especially concerning sovereign and non-sovereign functions. The evolution of the welfare state and pivotal judgments like *Nagendra Rao* have expanded state liability. Despite judicial advances, the absence of specific legislation remains a gap. The paper argues for the need for a comprehensive statute to clearly define the contours of state liability in a modern constitutional framework.

Keywords: Article 300, constitution, sovereign, constituent assembly, welfare state

Article 300 of the Constitution and its background

“The Indian Constitution was drafted by a Committee under the Chairmanship of Dr.

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Ambedkar and the Committee submitted its report on 21st Feb 1948.³ It was then adopted by the Constituent Assembly on 26th November 1949. Thereafter, it was signed by Dr. Rajendra Prasad as the President of the Constituent Assembly on 26th November 1949, and finally it came into force on 26th January 1950, which we celebrate as the Republic Day.

The initial Draft Constitution, under Clause 214, dealt with the matter of suits and proceedings against the State, which was on the lines of Section 176 of the Government of India Act, 1935. Clause 214 of the Draft Constitution read as follows:

“(1) The federation may sue or be sued by the name of the Federation of India and the Government of a Province may sue or be sued by the name of the Province and, may, subject to any provisions which may be made by Act of the Federal Parliament or a Provincial Legislature enacted by virtue of the powers conferred by this Constitution, sue or be sued in relation to their respective affairs in the like cases as the Dominion of India and the corresponding Province, might have sued or been sued if this Constitution had not been enacted.

(2) If at the date of the commencement of this Constitution any legal proceedings are pending to which the Dominion of India is a party, the Federation shall be deemed to be substituted for the Dominion in those proceedings.”⁴

However, the liability of the State was not defined. Clause 214 was later on revised as Article 274 of the Draft Constitution. Discussions were carried out in the Constituent Assembly of India on it. Dr. Ambedkar stated that the Government of India was not a legal entity, whereas the Union of India was a legal entity, with the power to sue as well as the liability to be sued. This amended form of Article 274 of the Draft Constitution was adopted, and it ultimately resulted in Article 300 of the Indian Constitution, 1950.

Article 300 of the Constitution of India

Article 300 of the Indian Constitution reads as follows:

“Suits and Proceedings - (1) The Government of India may sue or be sued by the name of the Union of India and the Government of a State may sue or be sued by the name of the State and may, subject to any provisions which may be made by Act of Parliament or of the Legislature of such State enacted by virtue of powers conferred by this Constitution, sue or be sued in relation to their respective affairs in the like cases as the Dominion of India and the corresponding Provinces or the corresponding Indian States might have sued or been sued if this Constitution had not been enacted.

- (2) If at the commencement of this Constitution-
- (a) any legal proceedings are pending to which the Dominion of India is a party, the Union of India shall be deemed to be substituted for the Dominion in those proceedings; and
- (b) any legal proceedings are pending to which a Province or an Indian State is a

³ Shiva Rao, *The Framing of Indian Constitution*. Bombay, Indian Institute of Public Administration 1968.

⁴ The Draft of Constitution of India, c. 214

party, the corresponding State shall be deemed to be substituted for the Province or the Indian State in those proceedings.”⁵

As it is clear, it was Article 300 of the Constitution which settled the suits and proceedings against the Union of India and the Government of the State. At the same time, this Article also empowers the respective Union and State governments to define their liabilities. “By the provision of the Constitution, the Union of India is a legal person.”⁶ In *State of Punjab v. O.C.B. Syndicate Ltd.*, the Supreme Court said that “it would not be correct to say that the Government is not a Constitutional or even juristic entity for the reason that it does not partake the characteristics or satisfy in whole, the definition of a corporation. The State is an organized political institution which has several of the attributes of a Corporation.”⁷

In *Union of India v. Mohin Chandra*, Ram Labhaya C.J. stated that “Article 300 clothes the Government of India with the status of a juristic person. It, therefore, could be sued. The only immunity that the Government of India enjoys, is for acts done in the exercise of sovereign functions.”⁸ Mahajan J. in *Provinces of Bombay v. Kushaldas Advani* defined the word sue as follows:

“The expression sue means the enforcement of a claim or a civil right by means of legal proceedings. When a right is in jeopardy, then any proceedings that can be adopted to put it out of jeopardy falls within the expression sue. Any remedy that can be taken to vindicate the right is included within the expressions.”⁹

“It is noticed that Article 300(1) consists of three parts. The first part deals with question about the form and the cause title, for a suit intended to be filed by or against the Union of India or the Government of a State. The second part provides *inter alia*, that the Union of India or a State may sue or be sued in relation to its affairs in cases like those in which the Dominion of India or a corresponding Provinces or an Indian State as the case may be, might have sued or been sued if the Constitution had not been enacted. The third part provides that it would be competent for the Parliament or Legislature of a State to make appropriate provisions in regard to the topic covered by the Article 300(1).”¹⁰

The Position of Union Territories

The Union and the States have been dealt with in Article 300 of the Indian Constitution. However, when it comes to the Union Territories, the Article is silent. Article 239 gives this administration power to the President. But he does not act as the head of the Union. Therefore, for the purpose of suits and proceedings, the Union Territories, though centrally ruled, cannot be coloured with the same brush as the Union.

In *Satya Dev v. Padma Dev*, it was held that “the Union Territory is a separate entity and the Government of a Union Territory and the Central Government are not identical. A suit by or against a Union Territory must therefore, be brought by or against the Government of the Union Territory and not in the name of the Central Government”.¹¹

⁵ The Constitution of India Act 1950, a 300

⁶ Union of India v. Satvendra Nath AIR 1955 cal. 581

⁷ State of Punjab v. O.C.B. Syndicate Ltd., AIR 1964 SC 669 at 669

⁸ Union of India v. Mohin Chandra A.I.R. 1952 Ass. 159 at 166.

⁹ Provinces of Bombay v. Kushaldas Advani AIR 1950 SC 222.

¹⁰ State of Rajasthan v. Vidhyawati, AIR 1962 SC 933 at 966.

¹¹ Satya Dev v. Padma Dev, AIR 1959 Tri. 41

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Article 300 does provide the power to the Parliament to enact a legislation to determine the liability of the State for the torts of its servants. In pursuance of it, the Parliament came up with the Government (Liability in Tort) Bill 1967¹². However, it could never be passed as an Act. The Supreme Court and High Courts then preferred to apply the principles applied in the Peninsular Case¹³ to decide the subject matter of vicarious liability of the State. According to it, the State is liable for the wrongs in terms of negligence of its servants, if the negligence is such as would render the State the position of an ordinary employer. The following can be a list of the grounds for deciding the liability of the State for the torts committed by its servants.

Grounds for fixing liability of the State under Judicial interpretations

Non-Sovereign Functions

Negligent driving

The State stands liable for the damages caused due to negligent driving of its servants while he is discharging any non-sovereign functions. The first post-constitutional instance of the application of the Peninsular case rule was in *State of Rajasthan v. Vidyawathi*¹⁴. The jeep driver of Udaipur's Collector had been sent to a workshop for necessary repairs of the jeep. While returning, due to his rash and negligent driving, he knocked down one Jagadishlal on the footpath of Udaipur city, who later on died of his injuries in the hospital. On suing by his wife, the Supreme Court held that the State was liable and was directed to pay damages. The Court found that "the accident took place while the driver was bringing the jeep back from the workshop to the Collector's residence. It cannot be said that he was employed on a task which was based on the delegation of sovereign or State powers of the State. His act was not an act in the exercise of sovereign function. The employment of a driver of a jeep for the use of a civil servant was an activity which was not connected in any manner with the sovereign power of the State."¹⁵ Thus, the Supreme Court upheld the sovereign function and the non-sovereign function distinction of the State. It expanded the liability of the State in favour of the wronged individuals.

However, this development was given a break in the case of *Kasturilal v. State of U.P.*¹⁶ "It was stated that the watertight compartmentalization of the State function into sovereign and non-sovereign is highly reminiscent of the laissez-faire era"¹⁷, while "the decision is hailed on the one hand for applying Sir Barnes Peacock's dictum rightly and thus clearing dead wood that hitherto blocked the way of progress."¹⁸ "It has been criticized that even after the commencement of the Indian Constitution, the doctrine is

¹² Bill no.43 of 1967(as introduced in Loksabha on 22.5.1967)

¹³ Peninsular and Orientation Steam Navigation Company v. Secretary of State for India, (1861) 5 Bombay H.C.R. App1

¹⁴ AIR 1962 SC 933

¹⁵ AIR 1962 SC 933 (find exact)

¹⁶ AIR 1965 SC 1039.

¹⁷ Alice Jacob, "Vicarious Liability of State in Torts", 7 JILI 247 (1965)

¹⁸ A.T. Markose, "State of Rajasthan v. Vidhyawati – Acceptance of Vicarious Liability by State for the Tortious Acts of State Servants. The Responsible State," Case note 4 JILI 280 (1962)

based on sovereign–non sovereign distinction”.¹⁹ It was also held by the Orissa High Court that “the State was vicariously liable for the tortious act committed by its servant”.²⁰

Malicious Prosecution

In *Maharaja Bose v. Governor General in Council*²¹, the plaintiff, while travelling in the defendant’s train, stopped it by chain pulling after being threatened by the soldiers on board. Later, he did not disclose his name and address to the employee of the defendant. So, he was arrested and his custody was given to the railway police. There was a trial and got acquitted. After the trial, he sued the defendant Governor General. The ground for the suit was for malicious prosecution. The Calcutta High Court adjudicated that the acts complained of by the plaintiff were just incidental to the running of the railways. So, they were not done while exercising the sovereign powers. Hence, the Governor General was made liable for paying damages for the malicious prosecution.

The Court determined that the claimant had no plausible excuse for breaking off the line of communication. Because the claimant failed to give his identity and address to the police, the defendant’s servant had a right to treat him. The defendant’s employees were discovered by the court to have genuine and justified suspicions of the plaintiff’s guilt and to have rejected the notion of malice. The lawsuit was dropped, and the government was absolved of responsibility for the employee’s behaviour.

In the case of *West Bengal State Electricity Board v. Dilip Kumar Ray*²², the appellant, West Bengal State Electricity Board (WBSEB), initiated disciplinary proceedings and lodged a police First Information Report (FIR) against respondent No.1, who was a Superintending Engineer. He was suspended on alleged charges of misconduct. Due to procedural delays and lack of timely chargesheet, respondent approached the High Court multiple times, leading to judicial directions for the supply of documents, commencement, and expeditious completion of the departmental enquiry. The enquiry ultimately exonerated the respondent of most charges, and the High Court, upon writ petition, set aside the suspension and directed reinstatement. Respondent No.1, thereafter, filed a civil suit against the Board and others for damages for harassment and injury to reputation, citing the mala fide institution of disciplinary and criminal proceedings and adverse newspaper publicity.

The Supreme Court examined the requirements for tortious liability of an employer for malicious prosecution, defamation, and harassment based on departmental action. It reiterated that “malice” in law signifies a wrongful act intentionally done without just cause or excuse, but for an action in damages for malicious prosecution, the plaintiff must plead and prove (i) lack of reasonable and probable cause; (ii) malice (i.e., improper or collateral motive); (iii) initiation of judicial proceedings; and (iv) termination in favor of the plaintiff. General, vague allegations of mala fides are insufficient-there must be cogent evidence showing improper motive or lack of reasonable cause.

The Court found that the plaintiff lacked specific averments of malicious prosecution, and neither the pleadings nor the evidence established the essential elements of the

¹⁹ A. Kuppaswamy, “States Liability for Employee’s Torts”, 30 SCJ 26 (1964)

²⁰ Amulya Patnaik v. State of Orissa. AIR 1967 Orissa 116

²¹ AIR 1952 Cal. 242

²² AIR 2007 SC 976

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tort. Both the trial court and the High Court had acknowledged that it was not established which officers were responsible for the wrongful acts, and the trial court itself found there was no actionable defamation. The High Court's reasoning was criticized as confusing and contradictory, especially since it treated damages for harassment as those for malicious prosecution without requisite findings.

The Supreme Court held that the awards for harassment and loss of reputation were unjustified and not supported in law or on the facts. The foundation for granting damages was absent, as there was no specific plea or proof of malicious prosecution or defamation, and the findings about "extraneous reasons" for suspension were based on surmises. Thus, the appeal was allowed, the judgments and decrees awarding damages were set aside, and no costs were awarded. The decision reaffirms the need for precise pleadings and strict proof of malice and want of reasonable cause in actions for malicious prosecution and similar torts.

Conversion of Property

The tort of conversion deals with the wrongful possession or use of someone else's property in a manner inconsistent with the owner's rights. In *Union of India v. Muralidhar*, the plaintiff's portion of the land was removed, and the same was placed on the railway track under construction. It was adjudged that "the Union of India was liable in conversion for the value of the earth belonging to the plaintiff even if the latter had made no demand for the return of the earth".²³ This case established a crucial precedent where the act of wrongful appropriation itself constituted conversion, making the Union liable for damages. It reflected the principle that the State, like any private individual, cannot unjustly interfere with another's property rights, irrespective of it being a sovereign function. The liability arises from the act of dominion over property without lawful justification. This judgment emphasized the evolving judicial approach to hold the State accountable even in matters traditionally guarded by sovereign immunity, especially where property rights are infringed.

In the case of *Vidya Devi v. The State of Himachal Pradesh*²⁴, the respondent, the state of Himachal Pradesh, forcibly acquired the land around 1967 for the construction of a road without following the due process of law. Vidya Devi was unaware of her rights with respect to her property, being an illiterate. She became aware of her rights to claim compensation when, in 2010, her neighbor claimed the same.

She filed a civil writ petition before the Himachal Pradesh High Court, claiming compensation with respect to her property as per the provisions of the Land Acquisition Act, 1894. The High Court in 2013 dismissed the petition on the ground that the matter involved disputes on questions of law and facts essential for determining the starting point of limitation, and also granted liberty to file a civil suit before the appropriate court. Aggrieved by the decision, Devi approached the apex judicial authority, the Supreme Court of India.

²³ AIR 1952 Ass. 141

²⁴ 2020 (2) SCC 569

The bench comprising Justice Indu Malhotra and Justice Ajay Rastogi, held that:

‘The State cannot dispossess a citizen of his property except in accordance with the procedure established by law. The obligation to pay compensation, though not expressly included in Article 300 A, can be inferred in that Article. To forcibly dispossess a person of his private property, without following due process of law, would be violative of a human right, as also the constitutional right under Article 300 A of the Constitution.’

The Supreme Court further held that since it had been in continuous possession of the property for more than 42 years, the state could not take plea of adverse possession and held that the ‘State cannot be permitted to perfect its title over the land by invoking the doctrine of adverse possession to grab the property of its own citizens, as has been done in the present case.’ Hence, the Honorable court directed the state of Himachal Pradesh to pay the necessary compensation to the aggrieved party.

Commercial Functions

With the functions of the state increasing to the level of a welfare state, it also resulted in an increase in the commercial functions of the state. In this scenario, there is no real marked distinction which exists between the sovereign and non-sovereign functions of the State, where most non-sovereign functions are of the nature of commercial functions. The State is held to be vicariously liable for the wrongs of its servants in carrying out the commercial functions. “Profit element is not a necessary ingredient of carrying on business, though usually business is carried on for profit.”²⁵ Courts have consistently ruled that the performance of commercial tasks does not entitle the State to claim special protection from liability, especially when such actions affect the rights and property of private individuals.

In the case of *Nagendra Nath Bora v. Commissioner of Hills Division*²⁶, the appellant N. Nagendra & Co. carried on a business in fertiliser and foodgrains under a license issued by the appropriate authorities. Its premises were visited by the Police Inspector, Vigilance Cell and huge stocks of fertilisers, foodgrains and even non-essential goods were seized. The court held that barring functions such as administration of justice, maintenance of law and order and repression of crime, etc., which are among the primary and inalienable functions of a constitutional Government, the State cannot claim any immunity. The act of seizure of goods for the public interest is under the welfare state functions and not under the primary functions.

With respect to the principle of vicarious liability, it was held that if the officers can be sued personally for negligence and misfeasance in the discharge of public duty, there is no rationale for the proposition that even if the officer is liable, the State cannot be sued. Now, since the doctrine has become outdated and sovereignty rests with the people, the state cannot claim any immunity. Thus, the State of Andhra Pradesh was directed to pay the appellants the amount as decided by the trial court with costs.

The decision underscored the principle that the government could be held liable for its actions, particularly when they infringed upon the rights of individuals. This case set a precedent for the application of governmental liability in India and established important

²⁵ Union of India v. Ladulal Jain AIR 1963 SC 1681

²⁶ AIR 1958 SC 398

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principles regarding the scope of sovereign immunity under Article 300 of the Constitution.

Banking Business

The doctrine of vicarious liability holds an employer or principal legally responsible for the wrongful acts of their employees or agents, provided such acts are committed within the scope of employment or authority. When the State undertakes commercial activities, such as running public enterprises, engaging in trade, or operating banks, then it functions like any private body corporate. In these cases, courts have consistently maintained that the State cannot hide behind the veil of sovereignty to escape liability.

It was held in the case of *State of Uttar Pradesh v. Hindustan Lever* that “Any private individual could run a banking business, by employing accountants and treasurers to receive money being credited to the accounts of other individuals or even of State departments by an agreement with them. The sub-treasury of the state will be deemed to conduct an ordinary banking business which any private individual could run and which was not referable to any activity involving the exercise of any sovereign function.”²⁷ This ruling implies that when the State engages in banking or similar financial operations, it is subject to the same legal duties and liabilities as any private banker would be. The absence of sovereign character removes the State’s shield of immunity, and it becomes fully accountable for negligence, mismanagement, or breach of duty arising out of such activities. This aligns with the broader principle that the State must be held responsible when acting in a capacity similar to a private individual or corporation.

This evolving judicial approach reflects a core democratic value that is no one, not even the State, is above the law. Under Article 14 of the Constitution, which guarantees equality before the law, the State cannot claim special treatment when it takes part in commercial or non-sovereign activities. Just like any private individual or company, the government must be held accountable for its actions. This helps ensure fairness, protects citizens’ rights, and provides legal remedies when people are harmed by state actions.

Nowadays, with the rise of involvement of government in businesses and public-private ventures, there is a growing expectation that the State must lead by example. Courts have increasingly stressed that the government should act transparently, responsibly, particularly when its decisions directly affect both public trust and private interests.

Railways

The Railways in India carry out a non-sovereign function. It is the liability of the Railway authorities to take the reasonable care of their passengers. The Department of Railway is discharging non-sovereign functions of the State. Section 93 of the Railways Act 1989 states that “the railway administration shall be responsible for loss, destruction, damage or deterioration, in transit, a non – delivery of any consignment, arising from any cause except the following (i.e.,) act of God, arrest, restraint or seizure under legal process, orders of restriction imposed by the Central Government or State by an officer

²⁷ *State of Uttar Pradesh v. Hindustan Lever* AIR 1972 All. 486

or authority subordinate to the Central Government or State Government authorized by it in this loyalty act or omission or negligence of the consignor or the consignee or the endorsee or the agent or servant of the consignor or consignee or endorsee, natural deterioration or wastage in bulk or weight due to inherent defect, quality or vice of the goods, latent defects, fire, explosion or any unforeseen risk.”²⁸

The Supreme Court adjudicated in the case of *State of Kerala v. G.M.S. Railway*, that “a suit for damages for non-delivery of goods, sent through the railway owned by the Government of India must be brought against the Union of India and not against the General Manager of the concerned railway.”²⁹

In the case of *Union of India v. S.S. Works*, the Supreme Court held that, “when consignments are booked at railway risk, the liability of the railway is that of a bailee. The onus of proving that the railway employees took the necessary amount of care and that they were not guilty of negligence rests on the railway authorities.”³⁰ Owing to this observation, the damages were awarded.

It is the duty of the railway to engage sufficient employees to watch the railway crossing to avoid unnecessary accidents. A proper danger signal must be displayed. The person engaged at the gate at the level crossing must take care. In *M/s. Krishna Goods Carriers (P) Ltd. v. Union of India*,³⁹ the question of tortious liability of the railways was raised. In this case, the gate at a level crossing was open. There was no danger signal to warn the public of the danger of any approaching train. A truck driver crossed the railway line and collided with a goods train running at full speed. As a result of the collision, the truck was damaged. The truck owner sued the railway for damages on account of negligence. The Delhi High Court, in the case of *M/s. Krishna Goods Carriers (P) Ltd. v. Union of India* decreed the suit, and held that “the law was well settled that where a railway line crosses a highway or public path, reasonable precaution must be taken to reduce danger to the public to a minimum. The nature of the precautions depends on the nature and circumstances. When the train is approaching, it is the practice of railway authorities to keep the gates at a level crossing closed. Any neglect of this customary precaution is evidence of negligence, which may render the authority liable to any person who is hit or hurt when the gate is open, the public is reasonably entitled to assume that no train is approaching and that the line may be crossed with safety. The Court said that open gates amount to an invitation that the plaintiff could safely pass and if he was injured, he was entitled to recover.”³¹

In the case of *Commissioner for Railway v. McDermitt*, the court held that “Railway authorities must take reasonable care to avoid injuring members of the public at a level crossing. If their servants do something which would lead a reasonable man to believe that it is safe to cross the line and the plaintiff thereupon attempts to cross and is run into by a train, there is evidence of negligence against the railway authorities”.³²

In *Prag Ice and Oil Mills Firm, Aligarh v. Union of India*, the court held that if it is the plaintiff’s own default, then the Railway authorities won’t be liable. The court adjudicated that “while the land beneath the railway is railway property and the public

²⁸ The Railways Act 1989, s 93

²⁹ *State of Kerala v. G.M.S. Railway*, AIR 1976 SC 2538

³⁰ *Union of India v. S.S. Works*, AIR 1976 SC 1414

³¹ *M/s. Krishna Goods Carriers (P) Ltd. v. Union of India* AIR 1980 Del, 92

³² *Commissioner for Railway v. McDermitt* (1967) AC 169

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have a right to cross the railway line at the point where a level crossing is provided, that does not necessarily imply a corresponding obligation on the railway to close all such level crossings by gates or other devices when a train passes that way. The public, while crossing the railway line, must be on the lookout for trains coming from either direction. The fact that the level crossing, carried a warning of the danger of coming trains was sufficient and a member of the public who crosses a railway line does so at his own risk.”³³

The issue regarding the safeguarding of level crossings was dealt by the Supreme Court in the case of *Union of India v. Lalman*. The court explained that “A level crossing is on the one hand a dangerous spot in view of the possible movement of trains, and on the other is an invitation to the passerby. This is a public crossing and not merely one by private accommodation. Therefore, it is the legal duty of the railway to assure reasonable safety. The most obvious way of doing it is to provide gates of chain barriers and to post a watchman who should close them shortly, before the train passes. But failure to do so is not by itself an act of negligence provided that the railway had taken other steps sufficient in those circumstances, to caution effectively a passerby of average alertness and prudence”³⁴.

The same principle was again upheld by the Supreme Court in the case of *Union of India v. United India Assurance Co. Ltd.*, where the Court stated “applying the common law principles, the railway must be deemed to be negligent in not converting the unmanned level crossing into manned one with gates having regard to the volume of rail and road traffic at the point.”³⁵

In *Chairman Railway Board v. Chandrima Das*³⁶, a Bangladeshi lady was raped by Railway employees within the railway premises. She was later on rescued by the Howrah police. Then, an advocate, Chandrima Das, filed a writ petition in the High Court of Calcutta to claim compensation. The High Court of Calcutta awarded Rs.10 Lakh to the victim and held the Railways vicariously liable for the crime. In the appeal, the Supreme Court emphasized that Article 300 stands for both citizens and non-citizens and an advocate could approach the Courts for the same.

Postal Service

In order to overcome the shortcomings of the Post Office Act of 1866, the Indian Post Office Bill was introduced in the Parliament, and it became an Act in 1898. Section 6 of the Indian Post Office Act, 1898 states that “the State shall not incur any liability by reason of the loss, misdelivery or delay of or damage to any postal article in course of transmission by post, except in so far as such liability may in express forms be undertaken by the Central Government as herein after provided, and no officer of the Post Office shall incur any liability by return of any such loss, misdelivery, delay or damage, unless he has caused the same fraudulently or by his willful act or default”.³⁷

³³ *Prag Ice and Oil Mills Firm, Aligarh v. Union of India*, AIR 1980 All 168

³⁴ *Union of India v. Lalman*, AIR 1975 SC 1265

³⁵ *Union of India v. United India Assurance Co. Ltd.*, AIR 1998 SC 640

³⁶ AIR 2000 SCC 988

³⁷ The Indian Post Office Act 1898, s 6

The extent of immunity and liability of the Post Office, first of all, became a point of discussion in the case of *Union of India v. Mohd. Nazim*. This case addresses pivotal issues pertaining to the liability of the Union of India in the context of international postal transactions, specifically involving value-payable articles (V.P. articles) between India and Pakistan. The crux of the dispute revolves around the non-payment of funds by the Pakistani government due to the suspension of the money order service post-1949, and whether such non-payment absolves the Indian Post Office of its financial obligations under the Indian Post Office Act, 1898. The Supreme Court held in this case that “the post office has been established under the provisions of a statute enacted by the Parliament. It is not an agent of the sender of the postal article for reaching it to the addressee. It is not a common carrier. It is really a branch of the public service providing postal services subject to the provisions of the Post Office Act and the rules made thereunder.”³⁸

Carried out by Private individuals

In the concept of a welfare State, the state in every way tries to carry out activities for the well-being and development of the citizens. These functions often extend beyond traditional sovereign roles to include healthcare, education, infrastructure, and social security. Sometimes, these activities are also carried out by private individuals either through delegation, partnerships, or outsourcing. To increase the scope of the liability of these individuals, the courts in recent times have made them liable for the justice to be meted out to the wronged individual. Courts have emphasized that when private individuals or organizations perform functions of a public character or enjoy state-like authority, they cannot escape legal scrutiny. This judicial evolution ensures that citizens' rights are protected and justice is served, regardless of whether the wrongdoer is a public official or a private delegate performing a welfare function.

The decision of the Supreme Court in *Ramakrishna Mission v. Kago Kumya*³⁹ is also highly instructive on the issue of amenability of actions of private entities to judicial review under Article 226 of the Constitution of India. In the said case, the issue before this Court was whether the Hospital run by the Petitioner Mission performed a public function that made it amenable to writ jurisdiction under Article 226. This Court found that the Hospital and the Mission were not amenable to writ jurisdiction under Article 226 since running a hospital would not constitute a public function. This Court further highlighted that even when a private entity performs a public function, the Court would be required to enquire as to whether the grant-in-aid received by the said entity covers a significant portion of its expenditure. This Court went on to declare that the regulation of a private body by a statute does not give it the colour of a public function. A public function was held to be one which is “closely related to functions which are performed by the State in its sovereign capacity.” Accordingly, it was held that the Hospital was not performing a public function since the functions it performed were not “akin to those solely performed by State authorities.” It was held that medical services were provided by private as well as State entities and therefore, the nature of medical services was not such that they could be carried out solely by State authorities.

Maintenance of Hospitals

³⁸ *Union of India v. Mohd. Nazim*, AIR 1980 SC 431

³⁹ (2019) 16 SCC 303

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In *Mohamed Shafi Suleman Kazi v. Dr. Vidas Dhondu Kavishwar*⁴⁰, the plaintiff's wife had been admitted to the hospital for the delivery of the child. The wife died because of the negligence of the Doctor who left the cotton swabs inside her body while operating. The plaintiff filed a suit, and the government hospital was held liable with the reasoning that it was a private welfare function which could be performed by private individuals as well.

However, in the case of *the Madras High Court in Etti v. Secretary of State*⁴¹, the court took a differing view. The child of the plaintiff was taken away by someone else from the government hospital. The police were unable to find the child. It was held that the act of maintaining a hospital for the welfare of the public was a sovereign function of the state, and the state cannot be held liable for it.

In the recent decision of *Achut Rao Hari Bhau Kodwa and another v. State of Maharashtra and others*⁴², the Government doctor and 4 the State were held liable because of the negligence of the said doctor in the hospital resulting in death of the patients, it was held that running of hospitals not being exclusive function of the Government, maintaining a hospital by Govt. would not be an exercise of sovereign power so as to enable to claim immunity from liability for the tortious acts of its hospital employees. Compensation was awarded to the family of the deceased reversing the decision of the High Court and affirming the decision of the Trial Court.

In the case of *State of Haryana v. Santra*⁴³, Smt. Santra, a poor woman with seven children, underwent a sterilization operation in 1988 at a government hospital in Gurgaon under a family planning scheme run by the State of Haryana. She was assured that she would not conceive again. However, due to incomplete sterilization she later gave birth to another child. She filed a suit seeking ₹2 lakhs as compensation for medical negligence and the costs of raising the child.

The trial court found negligence on the part of the doctor and awarded ₹54,000 with 12% interest per annum. The Supreme Court dismissed the appeal filed by the State of Haryana. It affirmed the concurrent findings of the lower courts that the sterilization operation was incomplete and conducted negligently. The court upheld the compensation and the ratio given by the Court was that the doctor was a government servant acting within the course of employment. Therefore, the State was vicariously liable for the negligence committed. The court held that the defence of sovereign immunity is not available in cases of negligence in non-sovereign functions like medical services.

Acts Carried out by Public Works Department

The acts involving the element of welfare, like various development-oriented constructions of roads and buildings, come within the ambit of the public works department. These works can also be carried out by private operators. So, the public works department cannot be said to be carrying out a traditional sovereign function.

In the case of *State of Madhya Pradesh v. Ram Pratap*, the plaintiff filed a suit for the

⁴⁰ AIR 1982 Bom. 27

⁴¹ AIR 1939 Mad. 663

⁴² (1996) 2 SCC 634

⁴³ (2000) 5 SCC 182

damages caused to him due to the negligent driving of the driver of the State Public Works Department. The State argued that it was carrying out a sovereign function. The Madhya Pradesh High Court rejected this argument and held that “most of the activities are carried out by private contractors. In that sense, it cannot be said that the department carries a sovereign function, which cannot be carried on by a private individual without the delegation of sovereign power. The State is thus held liable for damages arising out of the tortious act of the truck driver.”⁴⁴

The case *Chief Conservator of Forests v. Jagannath Maruti Kondhare*⁴⁵ involved casual workers employed by the Forest Department of Maharashtra under schemes like the Pachgaon Parwati Scheme and social forestry programs in Pune and Ahmednagar districts, which aimed at bio-aesthetic development, recreational and educational benefits, and environmental protection. The workers had been employed for 5 to 6 years but were not regularised and were paid less than permanent employees. The workers approached the Industrial Courts, alleging unfair labour practices under Item 6 of Schedule IV of the Maharashtra Recognition of Trade Unions and Prevention of Unfair Labour Practices Act, 1971, adopted from Section 2(j) of the Industrial Disputes Act, 1947.

The Court held that “the aforesaid scheme undertaken by the Forest Department cannot be regarded as a part of sovereign function of the State, and so, it was open to the respondents to invoke the provisions of the State Act.” The Court held that functions like afforestation and park creation, aimed at recreational and educational purposes, are not inalienable sovereign functions. Hence, such activities fall within the ambit of “industry” under Section 2(j) of the Industrial Disputes Act. Sovereign functions are limited to core state functions like defence, foreign affairs, and law and order, not welfare or environmental activities, which can be outsourced.

Reservoir Construction

The work of the construction of a reservoir is one which is of a private nature. In the case of *Andhra Pradesh v. Padma Rani*, the driver under the employment of the State Government was negligent and hit a jeep, resulting in the death of an engineer in the jeep. The State pleaded immunity because of sovereign function. However, it was not accepted by the Andhra Pradesh High Court. The court held that “the construction of the project is an undertaking (or activity entered into) by the State in pursuit of its welfare ideal and as such is not an activity in which the exercise of sovereign power is involved”.⁴⁶

Relief works in emergency

The question of whether the relief works carried out by the state in times of disaster or emergency came into question before the court in the case of *Indian Insurance Company Association Pool Bombay v. Radha Bai*. The question was whether such a work was traditionally within the ambit of sovereign function. It was held that such a function cannot be said to be a traditional sovereign function of the state. The Madhya Pradesh High Court stated that:

“These cases show that traditional sovereign functions are the making of laws, the administration of Justice, the maintenance of order, the repression of crime, carrying on

⁴⁴AIR 1961 Punj. 336

⁴⁵ AIR 1996 SC 2898

⁴⁶ AIR 1976 A.P. 122

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of war, the making of treaties of peace and other consequential functions. Whether this list be exhaustive or not, it is at least clear that the social, economic and welfare activities undertaken by a modern State are not included in the traditional sovereign functions."⁴⁷

Relief Work in famines

The question of whether the relief works carried out by the state in times of drought or famine came into question before the court in the case of *Shyam Sunder v. State of Rajasthan*. The Supreme Court held that "famine relief work was not a sovereign function of the State as it has been traditionally understood. This was a work which could be undertaken by private individuals, and there was nothing peculiar about it so as to predicate that the State alone can undertake the work. We do not pause to consider the question whether the immunity of the State for injuries to its citizens committed in the exercise of what are called sovereign functions has any moral justification today or whether there exists any rational dividing line between the so-called Sovereign and Proprietary or Commercial functions for determining State liability."⁴⁸ So, the Supreme Court favoured the plaintiff in this case and adjudicated that such a work was not included within the purview of the sovereign functions of the state.

Services in Fire Breakout

The wide scope of welfare actions carried out by the state does not mean that the state is immune to any torts caused due to the negligence of its servants in the name of sovereign functions. In the case of *State of Tamil Nadu v. P.K. Shamsudeen*, the Madras Fire Service Ambulance driver, while carrying out a rescue operation and rushing a victim of a fire breakout to the hospital, negligently hit a motorcyclist who died. The state claimed immunity in the name of sovereign function. The Madras High Court, rejecting the contention of the State, adjudicated that:

"The transporting of a patient to the hospital can be carried even by private individuals and when it is not the case of the State the transport of patients can only be done by the State in their vehicles, it cannot be said that the work of transporting a person who had been stabbed, to the hospital is a sovereign function. Having regard to these, it cannot be said that the State is immune from liability in respect of the accident caused by the driver of the Fire Service Ambulance van by his rash and negligent driving."⁴⁹

Liability of the State based on the Nature of the Work

Earlier, it was thought that every work related to the military was a sovereign function of the state, and the state had complete immunity from it. Later on, there was a progressive change where an increasing number of functions started to be included in the non-sovereign functions category, and the state started to be liable for it.

⁴⁷ AIR 1976 M.P. 164

⁴⁸ AIR 1974 SC 890

⁴⁹ AIR 1992 SC 1937

In the case of *McInerny v Secretary of State*⁵⁰, it was held that maintenance of public paths, routes are for public welfare and therefore do fall under the ambit of sovereign functions. Similarly, “maintenance of military roads, commandeering goods during the war, training for defense, arrest, and detention, the performance of military duties, maintenance of law and order, administration of justice and collection of revenues are a part of sovereign functions as laid down through various cases”.

In the case of *Satyawati v. Union of India*, a person was killed by the rash and negligent driving of the driver who was carrying the hockey and basketball teams of the military. The state pleaded immunity based on the sovereign functions. The Delhi High Court adjudicated that, “it is the nature of the activity that has to be seen in such cases, truly be called the exercise of sovereign power. So, carrying hockey and basketball teams to play a match can by no process of extension be termed as an exercise of sovereign powers. Therefore, the Union of India is liable for the damage suffered by the plaintiff.”⁵¹

Similarly, the Bombay High Court agreed with it held in the case of *Union of India v. Sugrabai*, that “no sovereign function was discharged by the State when records, sound ranging machine and other equipment were transported from the workshop to the School of Artillery through a military truck.”⁵²

On the same lines, it was held in the case of *Union of India v. Smt. Jasso* that “the transport of coal from some depot or store to the Headquarters building of the army at Shimla could be undertaken even by a contractor or by a private individual and that the mere fact that the State had chosen to undertake the transport by its army truck and the driver of the military vehicle cannot make any difference to the liability of the State for damages for the tortious acts of the driver.”⁵³

In the case of *Roop Lal v. Union of India*, Jammu and Kashmir High Court adjudged that “the carrying of the driftwood by the Jawans is not an act done in the course of their performance of military duties or for the purpose of any sovereign function and therefore, no immunity can be claimed in respect of such a tortious act.”⁵⁴

In *Union of India v. Kumari Neelam*, the negligent driving of the driver going to purchase vegetables for prisoner caused injuries to a girl child. The High Court of Madhya Pradesh held that, “where the work in question can be and is undertaken by private individuals, there is nothing peculiar about it to be called a sovereign activity. The Union of India cannot, therefore, be absolved from liability”.⁵⁵

The plaintiff in *Kuppanna Chetty & Co. v. The collector of Anantapur*⁵⁶ suffered a large loss as a result of the Tahsildar attaching the mobile items in violation of the Madras Revenue Recovery Act. The Court decided that the State is not responsible for any harm that a government employee suffers while performing a sovereign or exclusive State activity in accordance with the State's statutory mandate.

⁵⁰ [1911] ILR 38 Cal 797

⁵¹ AIR 1967 Del. 98

⁵² AIR 1969 Bom. 13

⁵³ AIR 1962 Punj. 315

⁵⁴ AIR 1972 J&K 22

⁵⁵ AIR 1980 MP 60

⁵⁶ AIR 1965 AP 457

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In *the State of Andhra Pradesh v. Ankanna*⁵⁷, a similar ruling was upheld. The plaintiff's bullock cart was purportedly improperly and intentionally held by income officials with the intention of realizing land tax under the Revenue Recovery Act. According to the Court, since the collection of land income was seen as a sovereign activity at the time the legislation creating the act was adopted, the State could not be held accountable for the dishonest activities of its workers.

According to the case laws mentioned above, the State cannot be held responsible for any misbehaviour perpetrated by a public official while they are allegedly performing authorized activities within the context of sovereign operations, such as collecting taxes, etc.

In the course of *Shivbhajan Durga Prasad v. Secretary of State*⁵⁸, the petitioner got wronged by the constable, the petitioner sued the Secretary of state for compensation. The court held that performance of statutory duty is a part of the sovereign function and hence was absolved from the charges. "The court did not hold the secretary responsible for the constable's conduct."

The Dichotomy Dilution of sovereign and non-sovereign functions

In the earlier days, the sovereign functions and non-sovereign functions concept was followed strictly. "In the modern welfare State, there is no dispute about the proposition that the victim of a wrongful act of a public servant committed in the course of his official duty should be indemnified".⁵⁹

The principle which stands out is that it is the prime responsibility of the state to compensate the citizens for any harm caused due to the actions of the state. This compensation has to be given irrespective of the nature of the functions carried out by the state. "While the protection of freedom of action dictates that the wrongdoer can be compelled to pay only if his activity was intentionally wrongful or negligent."⁶⁰

The strict dichotomy between the sovereign and non-sovereign functions has been diluted in the modern times. In the case of *Union of India v. Sugrabai*, the Court held that "we reject the argument that every act which is necessary for the discharge of a sovereign function involves an exercise of sovereign power. Many of these acts do not require to be done by the State through its servants. For example, the supply of food to the army may be transported in trucks belonging to private persons. Though the transportation of the machine from the workshop to the military school was necessary for the training of army personnel, it was not necessary to transport it through a military truck driven by defence personnel. The machine could have been carried by a private carrier. The increased activities of the State have made a deep impact on all facets of an individual's life, and therefore, the liability of the State should accordingly be made co-extensive with its modern role of a welfare State and not be confined to the laissez-faire era."⁶¹

⁵⁷ AIR 1967 AP 41

⁵⁸ AIR 1975 SC 957

⁵⁹ W. Fried Mann, *Law in a Changing Society*, 90-91(1st Indian Reprint, 1970)

⁶⁰ Joseph Minatur, *The Indian Legal System*, 7 (ILI Publication, New Delhi, 1978)

⁶¹ AIR 1969 Bom. 13

N. Nagendra Rao & Co v. State of Andhra Pradesh is one of the most landmark cases for showing the extent of immunity and liability of the State. The appellant carried out the business of food grains and fertilizers, and he had the necessary license for it. Even then, his goods were seized under the Essential Commodities Act, 1955. The Collector issued directions to return a substantial part of the goods to him and confiscate a nominal part. He was then asked to take the delivery of the released stock. At that time, the appellant found that the stock had been spoiled, both in terms of quantity as well as quality. The appellant thus demanded compensation. He got no response from the authorities regarding the same, and filed a suit for the same. The State claimed immunity, citing it as a sovereign function of the State.

The trial Court rejected the contention of the State and decreed the suit in part in favour of the appellant for the loss suffered by him. The State appealed the same before the High Court of Andhra Pradesh. The judgment of the trial court was reversed, and the state was adjudicated to have sovereign immunity.

The plaintiff thus appealed before the Supreme Court against the order of the High Court of Andhra Pradesh. The Supreme Court, adjudicating in favour of the plaintiff, held that "By virtue of Article 300, if a competent legislature enacts a law for compensation or damage for any act done by it or its officers in discharge of their statutory duty, then a suit against it would be maintainable. The Essential Commodities Act itself provides for the return of the goods if they are not confiscated for any reason. And if the goods cannot be returned for any reason, then the owner is entitled to the value of the goods with interest. When, due to the negligent act of the officers of the State, a citizen suffers any damage, the State will be liable to pay compensation, and the principle of sovereign immunity of the State will not absolve it from this liability. In the context of the modern concept of sovereignty, the doctrine of sovereign immunity stands diluted, and the distinction between sovereign and non-sovereign functions no longer exists. The dissatisfactory condition of the law in this regard suggests enacting appropriate legislation to remove the uncertainty in this area. The State was liable vicariously for the negligence committed by its officers in the discharge of public duty conferred on them under a statute. As regards the immunity of the State on the ground of sovereign function, the Court held that the traditional concept of sovereignty has undergone a considerable change in modern times, and the line of distinction between sovereign and non-sovereign powers no longer survives. No civilised system can permit an executive action to be exempted from liability, as it is sovereign. The concept of public interest has made structural changes in society. No legal system can place the State above the law, as it is unjust and unfair for a citizen to be deprived of his property illegally by the negligent act of officers of the State without remedy. The need for the State to have extraordinary powers cannot be doubted. But it cannot be claimed that the claim of the common man can be thrown out merely because the act was done by its officer, even though it was against the law. The needs of the State, the duty of its officials and the right of the citizens are required to be reconciled so that the rule of law in a welfare State is not shaken. In a welfare State, the functions of the State are not only the defence of the country or administration of justice and maintaining law and order, but it extends to regulating and controlling the activities of the people in almost every sphere, educational, commercial, social, economic, political and even marital. The demarcation between sovereign and non-sovereign powers for which no rational

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basis survives has largely disappeared. Therefore, barring functions such as administration of justice, maintenance of law and order and repression of crime, etc., which are among the primary and inalienable functions of a Constitutional State, the State cannot claim any immunity. The Sovereignty now vests in the people. The legislature, executive and the judiciary have been created and constituted to serve the people.”⁶²

The courts in successive cases continued with the policy of narrowing the scope of sovereign immunity, rather than attempt an express overruling of *Kasturilal*. Another important case in this regard is the case of *State of A.P. v. Challa Ramakrishna Reddy*. A prisoner was killed within the boundaries of the jail, even though he had informed the police authorities about apprehensions for his life. No action was taken by the prison authorities even after his apprehension.

The court further held that “The Maxim that King can do no wrong or that the Crown is not answerable in tort has no place in Indian jurisprudence where the power vests, not in the Crown, but in the people who elect their representatives to run the Government, which has to act in accordance with the provisions of the Constitution and would be answerable to the people for any violation thereof.”

The Supreme Court held that “in the process of judicial advancement of *Kasturilal's* case has played into insignificance and is no longer of any binding value. In case of violation of fundamental rights, the defence of sovereign immunity, which is an old and archaic defence, cannot be accepted and the State and the police are liable to compensate the victim.” Thus, the ratio of this case was that sovereign immunity, which is a statutory justification, cannot be applied in case of violation of fundamental rights, because statutory provisions cannot override constitutional provisions.

Conclusion

In conclusion, Article 300 of the Constitution plays a pivotal role in defining the legal personality and liability of the Union and State governments. The age-old rule, which was laid down in the *Peninsular and Oriental Steam Navigation* case⁶³ seems to be outdated today. That particular judgment was given at a time when the concept of the welfare state had not really developed to the extent of today's times. With the increase in the scope of the functions of the state, and the gradual evolution of the state from police to welfare, it is obvious that the state in today's times has a deep impact on the daily lives of individuals. This fact stretches the liability of the state from merely non-sovereign functions.

To further this object, the judgment in *Nagendra Rao* case⁶⁴ is a very important one in establishing the tortious liability of the State in a Modern Welfare State era. This judgment has risen above the concept of sovereign and non-sovereign functions, and at the same time fixed the liability of the State. The primary consideration here is whether the state is answerable to the judiciary in such matters. The state can exercise

⁶² AIR 1994 S.C.2663

⁶³ (1861) Bombay. HCR App 1

⁶⁴ *Nagendra Rao v State of A.P.*, AIR 1994 SC 2663

its immunity only when it is performing the external sovereignty, the political or defence functions.

However, there is only so much a judgment can do. Though the Parliament is empowered to make legislation on this subject matter, this wish remains eluded. This is one specific area where concrete legislation is definitely required to settle this long-standing dispute. While the Constitution and judiciary have laid a foundational framework, the changing nature of state function necessitates a re-examination of state liability. In the absence of clear statutory law, inconsistencies remain. It is imperative that the Parliament enacts a comprehensive legislation to codify state liability, ensuring transparency, accountability, and protection of citizens' rights.